

“ WHAT IS THE FRIENDSHIP AND WHO ARE SOULMATES?”

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Annotation: This article discusses what friendship is, when we find true friends and the conditions of true friendship.

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Friendship is a very multifaceted and complex concept. Everyone in the world can give completely different definitions to this word. People have been friends since ancient times. When a person is surrounded by close friends, it seems to him that he is not alone in this world, there is always someone to rely on, who can help in words and deeds in difficult times, and listen. Comrades are ready to come to the rescue, stand by their side even if they are wrong. Often people confuse the definition of "friendship" with another type of interpersonal relationship, expecting other unusual actions and words, which often leads to mutual disappointment. It is important to distinguish friendship from all other types of communication. Understanding and understanding what this means not only helps to become and remain a true, faithful, loyal friend, but also helps to properly evaluate the words and deeds of others, those we call friends. The essence of friendship What is friendship? According to the definition given in Ozhegov's explanatory dictionary, friendship is a high-level close relationship based on deep trust, mutual affection, common interests and views. A true comrade is deeply connected with his friend, can always count on mutual help, support, be loyal and honest in word and deed. This word always means a large amount of warmth, a high level of affection, trust and closeness. In psychology, friendship is classified as attraction. This word means "attraction to another person,

emotional attraction". These include: Man's need for communication and interaction prompts him to choose a variety of partners for himself. Different qualities of a partner that contribute to attraction and interaction. Relationship-building features that encourage further communication, trust, the search for meetings and the desire to connect life and destiny with a person. Some of the most famous features of its manifestation include: Understanding your friend's feelings, emotions and needs. A deep similarity of interests, up to the same perception of material objects, for example, objects of art. Complete separation of emotional, mental, moral, physical state. The ability to partially or completely replace other psychological support, conversation or just touch to significantly relieve mental pain. Sometimes empathy reaches such a level that people become almost the same attitude, thoughts and feelings. Such a perception not only helps to know your friend better, but also gives a higher pleasure than closeness, a sense of kinship in this infinite universe. What is meant by friendship? The word "friendship" has different meanings for many people. It may depend on how close a person wants to be to people. One calls fifty acquaintances a true friend, the other counts his comrades on his fingers. The third says that he cannot call anyone the word "friend". In ancient Greece, this concept was divided into two, emphasizing: friendship based on mutual interests and common goals of the community; The so-called "noble" friendship could only arise as a bond of high purity between two people. Today it is often called false friendship: Communication with friends. However, the most secret desires and deepest needs of such people, as a rule, are not believed. Expressing the unity and common interests of the team. Similarity of work or political activity. Empathizing with another person because of their isolation, uniqueness, and way of being different. You can call the word "friend" only a nice person, but such relationships are usually very unreliable, because people often change. The concept of "friendship" has no place in a relationship without trust, sincerity and love.

I didn't know what friendship was until I was 18 years old. I saw true friendship in one person. He is my university classmate Jasur. He is always ready to help me no matter what the situation is. In general, I can't be friends with someone easily. But Jasur and I have the same thoughts, if I'm happy, he's happy. If I'm sad, he's sad too. Until I was 18 years old, I never told anyone about my secrets, not even my family. To my daughters too. But I can easily tell everything to this friend. Unfortunately, when I said that now I have found a friend, Jasur wants to go to study in Korea. But even long distances cannot separate us. He promised to call me every day.

As a religious scholar pointed out, being a friend also has its own rules. One of them is to never lie to each other no matter what the situation. It's true that I may sound funny to someone with these words, but I want to be who I am. I always ask myself why I should be superficial. It's better not to be superficial than to be superficial. I have met all kinds of people in this university. Some are hypocrites, some are opportunistic. But I try not to pay attention to them.

I should also mention that I have not only Jasur, but also other close friends. One of them is Farzona. But I call him Farzon. Farzon is also very reliable, fair, and funny. I made him angry once. If I'm not mistaken, it was a Russian language lesson. I thought he laughed at me when I recited the poem. But I was wrong. Then we

didn't talk for about a week. We finally reconciled. Since then, our relationship is good. Even though I can't speak Russian perfectly, I always tried to complete the given topics.

Three points are particularly important for understanding the psychological differences between adult friendship and youth friendship: 1) the relative completion of the formation of self-awareness; 2) expanding and differentiating the field of communication and activity; 3) the appearance of new intimate attachments. The content and structure of friendly communication is also changing. Tolerance for diversity is one of the main indicators of the level of culture and intellectual development. This is also reflected in communication. Childhood friendships can be ruined over a trifle. Guys are already ready to put up with the shortcomings of their friends, but friendship itself is still understood as a common thing. Types of friendship Spiritual friendship is mutual enrichment and complementing each other. Each is delighted and surprised by the superiority of the other. In this way, he gives his friend the opportunity to receive the recognition he needs: if someone who recognizes this right appreciates and understands you, there can be nothing more beautiful than that. The most surprising thing is that each person considers himself completely different from the other and admires the qualities that he does not have. Creative friendship - both friends retain their distinct individuality. In addition, friendship helps to creatively complement the personality of each friend, giving full character to their individuality. Everyday friendship can exist and develop only in conditions of territorial proximity. Friends should live side by side, provide services to each other, ask for help, go to the movies together, or at least talk about this or that. As a rule, such friendship is strengthened by constant reasons for meetings. It can be a simple neighborhood or common work. For example, doctors are often friends with doctors. At first glance, it seems that family friendship is the complete opposite of creative friendship, but it is not. The fact that our friend becomes essentially a friend of the whole family is characteristic of the kind of friendship we

are considering. And if we talk about couples with children, we can definitely talk about friendship with families. Types of friendship. The concept of romantic friendship is very vague. It refers to the friendship of the Romantic period, including the period of "storm and stress" that preceded it, or is related to or related to the specific ideas of friendship that circulated among the German Romantic poets. Psychological type of "romantic personality". If we ignore the psychological nuances, then the romantic law of friendship, firstly, a sharp increase in the requirements for its closeness and expressiveness, and secondly, "true friendship" corresponds to the youth period of a person's life. means to connect with the part. . In erotic friendship, there is no place for temptation and the desire to control the fate of another, to have power over him. True erotic friendship is a dispassionate, noble impulse to improve yourself and help another. All the pros and cons without petty calculations, without the desire to hold, command, influence, control. A friend receives his friend kindly and tries to please him. It doesn't matter whether he was waiting for it or it came unexpectedly. A friend gives without asking and takes without asking. If erotica can master all this and sometimes succeed, it can live next to friendship. Otherwise, it will break it. Friendship is a relationship between people that anyone can create. Although it is not the same as a mother, father, sister, brother or other relatives, it is still one of the best human relationships. People who have best friends consider themselves to be the happiest people in the world. "Friendship is not a necessity like philosophy or painting...it has no survival value; it's something that gives more survival value".

A great friendship is irreplaceable — it can inspire you to grow into a better version of yourself. If you have a friend who motivates you, return the favor and be their number one cheerleader with one of these motivational friendship quotes.

"Friendship is the hardest thing in the world to explain. It's not something you learn in school. But if you haven't learned the meaning of friendship, you really haven't learned anything." — Muhammad Ali

“Don’t make friends who are comfortable to be with. Make friends who will force you to lever yourself up.” — Thomas J. Watson

“The most beautiful discovery true friends make is that they can grow separately without growing apart.” — Elisabeth Foley

“Each friend represents a world in us, a world possibly not born until they arrive, and it is only by this meeting that a new world is born.” — Anais Nin

“Life is partly what we make it, and partly what it is made by the friends we choose.”
— Tennessee Williams

“They may forget what you said, but they will never forget how you made them feel.” — Carl W. Buechner

“Find a group of people who challenge and inspire you; spend a lot of time with them, and it will change your life.” — Amy Poehler

“For beautiful eyes, look for the good in others; for beautiful lips, speak only words of kindness; and for poise, walk with the knowledge that you are never alone.” — Audrey Hepburn

“The best and most beautiful things in the world cannot be seen or even touched — they must be felt with the heart.” — Helen Keller

“Happiness can be found even in the darkest of times, if one only remembers to turn on the light.” — Dumbledore

Cute Friendship Quotes to Make You Both Smile

When your friends make you genuinely smile, it’s a beautiful and heartwarming thing. Sometimes sappy sayings are just the thing to make your friend feel special and appreciated. These adorable friendship quotes are sure to get a smile out of your friend.

True friends will never leave your side, during the best and the worst times. Oftentimes, your most loyal friends are also the ones who know how to bring out the best in you. Show your appreciation of their dependability and constant support with these friendship quotes fit for your true blue friend.

“The essence of true friendship is to make allowance for another’s little lapses.” — David Storer.

“The friend who can be silent with us in a moment of despair or confusion, who can stay with us in an hour of grief and bereavement, who can tolerate not knowing...not healing, not curing...that is a friend who cares.” — Henri Nouwen
“True friends aren’t the ones who make your problems disappear. They are the ones who won’t disappear when you’re facing problems.”

“A friend can tell you things you don’t want to tell yourself.” — Frances Ward Weller

“Best friends understand when you say, ‘forget it.’ Wait forever when you say, ‘just a minute.’ Stay when you say, ‘leave me alone.’ And open the door before you can say, ‘come in.’

“When it hurts to look back and you’re afraid to look ahead, you can look beside you and your best friend will be there.”

“Everyone hears what you say. Friends listen to what you say. Best friends listen to what you don’t say.”

“Don’t walk behind me; I may not lead. Don’t walk in front of me; I may not follow. Just walk beside me and be my friend.” — Albert Camus

“A strong friendship doesn’t need daily conversation or being together. As long as the relationship lives in the heart, true friends never part.”

“Friendship is always a sweet responsibility, never an opportunity.” — Khalil Gibran

“Friends...they cherish one another’s hopes. They are kind to one another’s dreams.” — Henry David Thoreau

“False friendship, like the ivy, decays and ruins the walls it embraces; but true friendship gives new life and animation to the object it supports.” — Richard Burtor.

“The only way to have a friend is to be one.” — Ralph Waldo Emerson

“My best friend is the man who in wishing me well wishes it for my sake.” — Aristotle

“My best friend is the one who brings out the best in me.” — Henry Ford

Deep Friendship Quotes for Tight Bonds:

There are some friends that have been there for you since day one, through the best and worst times. Celebrate those especially close friends with these profound friendship quotes. Find the perfect quote to warm your friend’s heart below.

“Everyone has a friend during each stage of life. But only lucky ones have the same friend in all stages of life.”

“That’s when I realized what a true friend was. Someone who would always love you — the imperfect you, the confused you, the wrong you — because that is what people are supposed to do.”

“Best friends share laughs, memories and inside jokes. They will always be honest and stand by your side no matter what. They wipe your tears, pick you up when you fall, and are forever a piece of your heart.”

“If ever there is tomorrow when we’re not together...there is something you must always remember. You are braver than you believe, stronger than you seem, and smarter than you think but the most important thing is, even if we’re apart... I’ll always be with you.” — Winnie the Pooh

“Ultimately the bond of all companionship, whether in marriage or in friendship, is conversation.” — Oscar Wilde

“A friend is a person with whom I may be sincere. Before him I may think aloud. I am arrived at last in the presence of a man so real and equal, that I may drop even those undermost garments of dissimulation, courtesy, and second thought, which men never put off, and may deal with him with the simplicity and wholeness with which one chemical atom meets another.”

In conclusion, it is very difficult to find a good friend in this world. But after finding a good friend, you should be able to appreciate him.

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